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Scanning the Issue

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The current issue of The European Journal of Research and Development (Vol 2, No 1, April 2022) contains 4 articles.

The paper “Diagnosis Prediction of Construction Vehicles and Model Explainability Industry 4.0 Implementation” that has four authors who are Esra Akca, Prof. Dr. Semra Erpolat Taşabat, Tayfun Özçay, and Nermin Yalçı

The paper “Investigation of Physical and Liquid Performance Properties of Feminine Hygiene Pad in Commercially Used” that has four authors who are Ebru Çelikten, Kubilay Özden, Mehmet Daşdemir, and Tülin Kaya Nacarkahya.

The paper “Opportunities of on-demand logistics operations” that has four authors who are Polina Görbe, Tamás Bódis, Csaba Hencz, and Adrián Horváth.

The paper “Smart Supply Chains- A Futuristic Business Scenario” that has two authors who are Sadia Samar Ali and Rajbir Kaur.